

**RESEARCH OF TECHNOLOGIES OF RINGS MADE OF COMPOSITE
MATERIALS.**

Akbarjon Baymirzaev

*PhD, Department of Materials Science and Technology of New Materials, Andijan
Machine-Bulding institute, Andijan, Uzbekistan*

Email id: akbarshoxashox@gmail.com

Annotation. "ANDIJON ENERGO TAMIRLASH" LLC was selected as a research enterprise based on the casting of material for bearing rings. The main indicators of the research conducted on the technological basis are based on the casting detail obtained there.

Activities that can be performed at a research facility include processes ranging from melting ingots to machining them.

Keywords: research, technological, material, shaft, hardness, content, vacuum, impact viscosity, bearing details, ring, casting method.

Introduction

Bearings operate under conditions of very high contact stresses, reaching 6000 MPa in some cases. Therefore, bearing steels should have a dense homogeneous structure (macrostructure), minimal amounts of non-metallic inclusions, and minimum carbide should not be uniform.

Non-metallic inclusions in bearing steel not only reduce the durability of bearings, but they are also reflected in some other indicators of bearing quality. For example, with significant contamination of iron with non-metallic inclusions, it is almost impossible to obtain a high cleanliness class of the surface of the bearing parts. Contamination of steel with non-metallic additives in tool bearings leads to loss of ease of rotation, increase of "starting torque".

Material and Methods

One of the important indicators of the quality of steel, which determines the performance of bearings, is the macro, in particular, the axial and general porosity of the metal. The idea that it is not particularly harmful is a mistake. This is based on the fact that the axial zone of the metal does not protrude into the working surface of the bearing parts.

In the next sections of this chapter, we will learn about bearing ring material extraction technologies and their differences

Results

This method is used to obtain bearing rings in large sizes. It is not possible to get such large sizes in GKM. Such bearing rings, obtained in the technology of individual production, do not lead to economic efficiency

The bearing rings obtained by the free hammering method are made at the production facilities (pneumatic, steam compressors) with the help of workbenches, and using the universal tool equipment, they have only a cylindrical shape. It is necessary to heat and punch the center of the prepared cylindrical part in one more process. It was necessary to go through more complex technological processes to make the resulting ball into a correct cylindrical shape again. Force punching metal has also had problems.

Discussion

The free hammering method has been considered the main technological process only for individual and small series production. In this case, during heating and free hammering, soot is formed on the surface of the detail, and mechanical processing is necessary. Later, cutting the raw material to size is performed on another machine and is a labor-intensive process.

Removal of bearing rings is carried out automatically by GKM and krivoship connecting rod mechanisms and hammers. In this case, the upper part of the raw material is cleaned from soot by drab (with the help of steel balls in the drum), then

it is heated again at 1250oC, then it is re-stamped by volume stamping method (GKM) and continuous production of bearing rings is carried out.

Conclusion

Under laboratory conditions, hammering, stretching, and pressure treatment of metals with a force of 1.6kn in a hydraulic press were carried out in the workshop of steel and alloys.

Production of continuous cast steel for industrial and production use by hammering is carried out at the Volgograd bearing plant, with a hammer size of 500-400mm. The implementation of such technology was applied to parts with small bearing ring sizes.

REFERENCES

1. Rustamjan ogli, Baymirzayev Akbarjon, and Nazarova Ruxsora Shuxratjon Qizi. "TEKNOLOGIYALARNIGINA EMAS, ILM-FANNITUSHUNADIGONFUQAROLAR KO'PROQ BO'LISHI KERAK." BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI 2.4 (2022): 442-445.
2. Baymirzaev, Akbarjon. "Research on the Production of Bearing Details in a Modern Method." International Journal on Integrated Education 4.3: 269-271.
3. Baymirzaev, Akbarjon. "Obtaining And Efficiency Of Steel Casting In Local Conditions In Mechanical Engineering." Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research 2.09 (2021): 21-25.
4. Mamtjonovich, Tojiboyev Begijon, et al. "TO CREATE A TECHNOLOGY FOR OBTAINING THE DETAILS OF BEARINGS USED IN INDUSTRY FROM METAL-COMPOSITE MATERIALS."
5. Baymirzayev Akbarjon, Cr, Brands C. Si Mn, and CP Ni Si. "Production of Bearing Parts by Means of Vacuum Casting."
6. Baymirzaev, Akbarjon. "INVESTIGATION OF INNOVATIVE USE METHODS IN BEARING RINGS MANUFACTURING" AMERICAN

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE "THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC
PROGRESS "

2022 Warsaw, (Poland)

JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT (AJSLD)

2835-2157